

Postoperative complications and their prevention in surgery for cicatricial tracheal stenosis

Bakhromova Odina Alisherovna

Master's degree, Tashkent Medical Academy, Faculty of General Surgery
Uzbekistan, Tashkent.

E-mail: azimbaevaodina4@gmail.com

Eshonkhodjaev O.D - Associate Professor of Medical Sciences

Khayaliev R.Y. - Associate Professor of Medical Sciences

Tursunov N.T - Associate Professor of Medical Sciences

Rikhsiev Z.G - Doctor of the Department of Lung and Mediastinal Surgery

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Annotation: The basis for solving the problem of cicatricial tracheal stenosis (CTS) is its prevention, early diagnosis of the pathological process after prolonged mechanical ventilation and tracheostomy in intensive care units. The measures described above make it possible to diagnose narrowing of the trachea at the stage of granulation stenosis and ensure its correction using endoscopic intervention, avoiding traumatic operations. With the development of tracheal surgery, fundamentally new operations that were previously considered impossible were introduced into clinical practice: “two-level”, repeated resection of the trachea, resection of the trachea with simultaneous separation of the tracheoesophageal fistula. Combined, staged

techniques are used, when tracheoplastic operations or endoscopic interventions are performed as a stage before radical surgery - circular resection of the trachea (CRT). However, a single developed algorithm for the prevention and relief of postoperative complications in PCT surgery does not exist today. The further development of tracheal surgery directly depends on the development of a set of preventive measures aimed at preventing the development of complications and identifying unfavorable factors that increase the risk of developing the latter. In this regard, ongoing research in this direction is very promising and promising.

Keywords: cicatricial tracheal stenosis, trachea surgery, circular resection of the trachea.

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The most important direction in the development of tracheal surgery is to further improve the safety of surgical interventions by reducing the number of postoperative complications and mortality. The relevance of this issue increases in the context of the annual increase in the number of patients with PCT, the introduction into surgical practice of fundamentally new types of surgical interventions, such as repeated and two-level resection of the trachea, resection of the trachea with simultaneous dissociation of the tracheoesophageal fistula.

Surgical techniques for tracheal interventions have improved since the development of tracheal surgery in the mid-20th century, reducing the risk of

postoperative complications and mortality. Patients receive care in multidisciplinary specialized centers, where a multidisciplinary approach is implemented with the participation of a thoracic surgeon, anesthesiologist, endoscopist and otolaryngologist.

Suppurative complications in tracheal surgery are quite common. Their frequency varies, according to various authors, from 3 to 10%. This is due to the opening of the airway during surgery and contamination of the surgical wound. There are no studies in the world literature that would provide a comparative assessment of surgical wound contamination depending on the option for ensuring gas exchange.

Complications after circular resection of the trachea with anastomosis

Despite the successes of tracheal surgery, the incidence of complications after resection operations varies from 9 to 45%, and mortality - from 0 to 5% [10 11, 17, 47, 48, 59, 60, 61]. The persistence or history of tracheostomy is an unfavorable factor and increases the incidence of postoperative complications [47]. However, sometimes opposite results are reported. Thus, H. Auchincloss and D. Mathisen indicate 18.5% of complications in patients who underwent resection for post-intubation genesis of tracheal stenosis, when the patient did not have a tracheostomy. During interventions for idiopathic stenosis, the incidence of complications is significantly lower (6.6%), despite the fact that “high” laryngotracheal resections were performed [38]. Resection of up to 50% of the entire length of the trachea is relatively safe. A more extensive resection is associated with the risk of postoperative complications from the tracheal anastomosis [39, 43, 48, 62].

The unfavorable course of the postoperative period after CRT is divided into complications associated with tracheal anastomosis, purulent-inflammatory complications, complications from the larynx, and also nonspecific complications [10, 11, 47, 48]. Complications of the tracheal anastomosis mean failure of its sutures with the subsequent development of a purulent-inflammatory process. This development of events is associated with high tissue tension in the area of the tracheal anastomosis during extensive resections, and impaired blood supply to the trachea due to excessive mobilization of its walls. Failure is manifested by hemoptysis, stridor, subcutaneous emphysema or suppuration of the surgical wound, in various combinations. If there is a suspicion of failure of the tracheal anastomosis sutures, the first priority is to ensure adequate breathing and stabilize the lumen. Laryngotracheoscopy allows you to assess the size of the defect in the anastomosis. If the size is small, repeated surgery is not indicated. The patient is prescribed a voice mode (silence), undergoes antibacterial therapy and, if necessary, drains the area of the tracheal defect. If the defect is large or this therapy is ineffective, repeated intervention with the formation of a tracheostomy and the introduction of a T-shaped or tracheostomy tube is indicated [43]. A purulent-inflammatory process in the mediastinum can lead to the most serious complication - erosive bleeding from the great vessels into the lumen of the tracheobronchial tree as a result of the formation of a tracheovascular fistula. This complication is often fatal and requires emergency intervention in the amount of complex vascular reconstruction and exclusion of the affected area of the vessel from the bloodstream [63, 64].

Laryngeal complications include upper airway edema and laryngeal paralysis due to intraoperative injury to the inferior laryngeal nerves. Laryngeal edema often develops after laryngotracheal resections. Patients complain of hoarseness and noisy breathing. Fibrolaryngotracheoscopy allows you to assess the condition of the larynx and exclude complications directly from the anastomosis. In most cases, laryngeal edema is controlled by conservative therapy, which includes antibacterial drugs, glucocorticosteroids, diuretics and inhalation therapy. This therapy can be supplemented with nasotracheal intubation with a small-diameter tube without a cuff [65].

Intraoperative damage to the laryngeal nerves remains a serious complication of tracheal surgery. Precision isolation of the trachea as close to its side wall as possible avoids this. However, even if the recurrent laryngeal nerves are preserved, there is a risk of developing transient innervation disorders due to their traction or postoperative perineural inflammation. The complications described above can be managed with conservative therapy. In case of development of bilateral laryngeal paralysis, tracheostomy is indicated. Reconstructive intervention on the vocal larynx is recommended to be performed no earlier than 6 months after circular resection of the trachea [11, 65].

Complications after staged tracheoplastic interventions

During staged reconstructive plastic surgery (ERPO), in contrast to resection methods, the pathologically altered segment of the trachea is preserved, from which a satisfactory airway lumen is subsequently formed. ERPO is in demand in patients in whom resection is not possible for technical reasons or due to

concomitant diseases. In addition, their use in a multi-stage treatment algorithm makes it possible to reduce the size of the removed tracheal segment in case of extended or multifocal tracheal stenosis [42, 66, 67, 68]. The disadvantages of this treatment option are its long duration and the need for repeated operations. For these reasons, preference is often given to resection techniques or endoscopic intraluminal interventions, such as cryodestruction, electrical dissection of scars, laser and argon plasma coagulation [69, 70, 71]. In this regard, in recent years, publications about this method of treatment have practically not been found in Western literature or appear only in the otorhinolaryngological literature. Most complications after ERPO are purulent-inflammatory in nature: suppuration of the postoperative wound, failure of the skin-tracheal sutures, exacerbation of tracheobronchitis. This is due to the operation being performed under conditions of relative sterility, because the breathing circuit remains open throughout the entire intervention, as well as in the postoperative period [3, 66]. These operations are characterized by almost the same range of dangerous postoperative complications. Thus, arrosive bleeding from the brachiocephalic arterial trunk, developing as a result of the formation of a tracheovascular fistula, is also possible after tracheoplasty with a T-tube [49, 63, 64].

Complications after endoscopic operations

A relatively simple and effective method of endoscopic dilatation of the lumen of a narrowed airway is bougienage with a rigid bronchoscope tube, including for multifocal and extended stenoses [8, 35, 72]. To do this, tubes of increasing diameter are used sequentially. Endoscopic dilation of a narrowed tracheal segment

may be complicated by transmural rupture and/or bleeding [73]. In case of perforation of the membranous wall of the trachea, tracheal intubation is indicated with localization of the cuff of the endotracheal tube distal to the injured area. Thus, it is possible to turn off the affected area from ventilation, reduce the intraluminal air pressure in this area and avoid purulent-inflammatory complications (cellulitis of the neck and mediastinitis). If such manipulation is impossible due to the transition of the rupture of the membranous wall of the trachea to the main bronchi or the large extent of the rupture, surgical intervention is indicated [56, 71, 74]. Bleeding from the tracheal mucosa, resulting from rupture of scar tissue, is usually stopped by applying pressure with an inflated cuff and hemostatic therapy. In order to reduce tissue bleeding during endoscopic manipulations on the mucous membrane of the tracheobronchial tree, methods of cryodestruction and electrocoagulation, laser dissection of scars have been developed. In case of RCT, the cryosurgical method has not found widespread use due to the duration of the required exposure, low efficiency, and high risk of restenosis. The advantages are good patient tolerance and low risk of bleeding [35].

Electrosurgical and laser techniques have a number of significant disadvantages: non-radical manipulation and high relapse rate, the possibility of bleeding when removing the electrode due to the separation of the formed scab, the possibility of damage to the tracheal wall with the risk of perforation, and an increase in the extent of scar changes. Both methods are not widely used, respectively, due to low efficiency and the risk of possible complications [10].

To maintain the lumen of the trachea in the area of narrowing, endoscopic stenting is used, which can be considered as part of a combined staged treatment of PCT. Endoprosthesis has gained high popularity since 1989, when J.F. Dumon proposed a silicone linear self-fixing endoprosthesis with staggered protrusions on the outer surface that prevent its displacement [75]. Metal tracheal stents are not recommended for benign processes, including cicatricial stenosis, and should be used only if surgical treatment is impossible and stenting with a silicone endoprosthesis is ineffective. The use of metal endoprostheses as a stage treatment (“bridge”) before circular resection of the trachea is not recommended, because their removal may result in bleeding or perforation of the tracheal wall by the embedded coils of metal wire [56]. A frequent complication of tracheal endoprosthesis is stent dislocation and obstruction with secretions. Silicone structures move more often. Thus, the dislocation rate of Dumont stents is 9.5%, and the rate of obstruction is 3.6%. This necessitates the need to control the position of the stent and its sanitation endoscopically [76].

Conclusion:

Thus, the basis for solving the problem of cicatricial tracheal stenosis is its prevention, early diagnosis of the pathological process after prolonged mechanical ventilation and tracheostomy in intensive care units. The measures described above make it possible to diagnose narrowing of the trachea at the stage of granulation stenosis and ensure its correction using endoscopic intervention, avoiding traumatic operations.

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